

MEDICAL SCIENCES

OTOLARYNGOLOGICAL POST-COVID COMPLICATIONS

**Yakovets K.,
Hluhovska S.,
Yakovets R.,
Chornenka Zh.**

Bukovinian State Medical University, Ukraine

Abstract

Currently, many Ukrainians have experienced or are experiencing the unpleasant consequences of the infection and continue to fight them. Therefore, the issue of recovery after Covid is relevant. Some patients, even after recovery, are unable to quickly return to a normal active life and are forced to recover for weeks and sometimes months from the "stroke". Post-Covid symptoms are observed not only in the elderly and those with chronic diseases (cardiovascular, respiratory, diabetes, etc.), but increasingly in young people, even if they are asymptomatic or mild. Thus, the post-covid syndrome is a complex problem that requires the involvement of a number of specialists.

Keywords: *otolaryngology, COVID-19, post-Covid symptoms, complications*

Although COVID-19 is a respiratory infection, doctors acknowledge that the disease is multisystem, simply put, it can affect any organ. And its consequences are faced by all doctors - from ordinary pulmonologists to trichologists and psychiatrists. Coronavirus infection has conditional periods. Acute disease is usually limited to four weeks, but there are patients who are on lung ventilation for several months. The second stage lasts from four to twelve weeks, when some symptoms of the disease persist. Complaints that occur after 12 weeks of illness are long-term changes.

Most people infected with SARSCoV-2 carry mild or moderate disease and recover without special treatment. However, in some patients, COVID-19 disease can lead to severe complications. One of them is a violation of blood coagulation in the direction of hypercoagulation, which can be manifested by thrombosis of various localizations, including aseptic thrombosis of the arteries of the ENT organs and face.

Loss of smell has become a hallmark of COVID-19. At the very beginning, it was frightening, then it became a reason for jokes, and then it turned out that the COVID-19 passes, but the smells do not return. Not to all, however, to some.

There is a category of people whose sense of smell returns quickly. There are those to whom the sense of smell returns, but they do not feel the whole spectrum of smells. And there are indeed long-term disorders of smell and taste (in our study, we did not meet patients whose sense of smell or taste sensations would not be restored at all), but often there is a violation of the sensitivity spectrum or some note that a familiar smell is felt differently.

There are several theories why this happens. For example, there is a version that the peripheral part of the olfactory nerves is affected, and someone says that the olfactory bulbs themselves are affected. But there is no convincing evidence base. But it is known how often odors leave covid patients for a long time - the symptom persists for more than three months in 20% of those who have recovered.

We have encountered such disorders before - for example, with a chronic form of anemia, this can happen in some patients, with a deficiency of certain vitamins, with damage to the olfactory bulbs, with damage to the brain. That is, for medicine this is not new, but with respiratory infections, that is, so widely, we have encountered this for the first time.

Another problem is the development of neurosensory deafness, which may not be diagnosed initially due to the prevalence of respiratory symptoms or occur after some time. The neurotoxic effects of SARS-CoV on hearing have been insufficiently studied. It is known that some viruses have neurotoxic effects and can cause olfactory disorders, hearing loss, including parainfluenza virus, Epstein-Barr virus, human immunodeficiency virus, some coronaviruses. There is information about the development of sensorineural hearing loss in patients and the impact of coronavirus infections on the central nervous system, in particular on the involvement in the pathological process of the brain stem. Some viruses can directly damage the structures of the inner ear, others - to act indirectly. As a rule, deafness of viral etiology in form is sensorineural, but the development of conductive and mixed forms is possible.

Harmful action of the viral agent is directed to the peripheral part of the auditory analyzer, but central disorders of the auditory conduction pathway are not excluded. The mechanism of harmful effects on the peripheral department includes direct damage to the spiral organ, vascular strip or spiral ganglion. The indirect mechanism of damage is related to the production of antibodies to viral capsid proteins or immunodeficiency of the patient, which results in the development of secondary bacterial infection in the inner ear.

Patients infected with SARS-CoV-2 have a wide range of ENT-related symptoms. The study showed that the virus most often causes olfactory and taste disorders in the otolaryngological system. In our study, we evaluated the frequency of all ENT symptoms in patients admitted to the COVID department in the active phase of the disease. The frequency of olfactory and

taste dysfunctions was also assessed in these patients. A comparison of patients with and without olfactory / gustatory dysfunction was performed.

The rapid increase in the number of patients with COVID-19, as well as the number of deaths due to infection, is a major burden on the health care system. Thus, early detection followed by rapid isolation of infected patients can help prevent disease transmission and reduce disease severity. Therefore, it is very important to know all the symptoms caused by the disease. In cases of severe disease, patients may develop viral pneumonia and acute respiratory distress syndrome (ACS), which can lead to death despite treatment.

In our study, all patients with COVID-19 who were in the active phase of mild or moderate disease were evaluated for ENT-related symptoms. The most common symptoms of otorhinolaryngology were sore throat (49.21%), rhinorrhea (34.92%), sneezing (33.33%), changes in olfactory perception (36.51%), changes in taste perception (47.62%) and headache (30.16%). A study by Erdal Sakalli and others concluded that different frequencies of symptoms were: headache (56.4%), nasal congestion (53.5%), olfactory loss (51.2%), sore throat (50, 2%), loss of taste sensitivity (47.1%) and rhinorrhea (38.5%).

In a similar study in Italy in patients with mild COVID-19, all participants were interviewed for their symptoms by telephone and tested for Sino-Nose 22 (SNOT-22). The most common symptoms were fever (55.9%), cough (60.4%) and fatigue (68.3%), while upper respiratory symptoms were nasal congestion (41.1%) and sore throat. (31.2%) loss of olfactory and taste sensations (64.4%).

Various physicians, including otorhinolaryngologists, have reported anosmia or hyposmia, as well as ageusia or dysgeusia as symptoms of COVID-19. In this study, we also assessed the frequency of olfactory and taste dysfunction. In our study, 32.86% of patients reported olfactory dysfunction, 42.86% reported taste dysfunction, and 17.14% of patients reported both olfactory and gustatory dysfunction. It was also found that rhinorrhea and sneezing were significantly more common in patients with olfactory dysfunction. A parallel survey of olfactory and taste disorders in Milan, Italy, found that 33.9% of patients had at least one taste or olfactory dysfunction, while 18.6% of patients had both olfactory and taste dysfunction. In a study by Yan C. et al., It was noted that 68% of patients had altered sense of smell and 71% had altered taste. Jerome R. and others studied 417 patients with mild to moderate COVID-19 disease and found that 85.6% and 88.0% of patients reported olfactory and gustatory dysfunctions, respectively.

The pathophysiological mechanisms that cause olfactory and taste disturbances in patients with COVID-19 are considered to be tropism of the SARS-CoV-2 virus, which penetrates olfactory cells by signaling the interaction between its adhesion protein and ACE 2 protein on nasal epithelial target cells. Two main mechanisms of infection are considered: infection of the neuronal olfactory receptor with subsequent anterograde transport of the virus to the olfactory bulb and diffusion through channels in the cells covering the olfactory,

thus forming an open connection with the central nervous system.

Also, 14.28% of patients had ear-related symptoms that included hearing fullness, tinnitus, and hearing loss. 11.11% of patients had hearing fullness and 3.17% had tinnitus, and 6.35% had hearing loss that was either first-seen or worsened after COVID-19. A study by Francesco Freni et al showed that COVID-19 infection had a detrimental effect on snail hair cells and cochlear cell function, even in patients with mild symptoms. It is still unclear whether COVID-19 affects the auditory system or not, but this study, like other studies, examines the possible effects of this new viral infection on the auditory system.

The recipe for returning odors is still the same: nasal lavage with a special isotonic solution and olfactory training. To make them is quite simple: take 3-4 different essential oils, apply a couple of drops on napkins and sniff each. Try to remember the smells and why they belong - lemon, fir or something else. When you can at least slightly distinguish one cent from another, try to mix the samples so that you do not know where what is, and determine what exactly smells like a napkin.

The British Society of Otolaryngologists has found that olfactory training is effective in restoring the sense of smell. This means that you need to inhale the aroma of smells familiar to you from 2 times a day, for about 5 minutes. For example, the smell of coffee, citrus. For these purposes, you can use essential oils (fir, eucalyptus, roses). Even if you can't smell it, don't get frustrated and don't quit exercising. When you inhale a scent and mentally recall it, the neural connections in your brain re-learn to perceive the smell.

Conclusion. Knowledge of ENT symptoms in patients with COVID-19 will help identify the virus in the early stages and therefore limit further transmission of the virus. Manifestation of anosmia or hyposmia, ageusia and hearing loss in patients infected with SARS-CoV-2 may also act as an important tool and help in early isolation and early initiation of COVID-19 therapy.

REFERENCES:

1. Sakalli E, Temirbekov D, Bayri E. Ear nose throat-related symptoms with a focus on loss of smell and/or taste in COVID 19 patients. *Am J Otolaryngol.* 2020;41(6):102622. doi: 10.1016/j.amjoto.2020.102622.
2. Lechien JR, Chiesa-Estomba CM, Ayad T, Saussez S, Horoi M, Le Bon S D, et al. Olfactory and gustatory dysfunctions as a clinical presentation of mild-to-moderate forms of the coronavirus disease (COVID-19): a multicenter European study. *European Arch Oto-Rhino-Laryngol.* 2020;277:2251–2261. doi: 10.1007/s00405-020-05965-1.
3. Vaira LA, Salzano G, Deiana G, De Riu G. Anosmia and ageusia: common findings in COVID-19 patients. *Laryngoscope.* 2020;130(7):1787. doi: 10.1002/lary.28692.
4. Joanna Krajewska (Wojciechowska), Wojciech Krajewski, Krzysztof Zub, Tomasz Zatoński (2020) Review of practical recommendations for

otolaryngologists and head and neck surgeons during the COVID-19 pandemic. *Auris Nasus Larynx* 47(4) 544-558.

5. Spinato G, Fabbris C, Polesel J, et al. Alterations in smell or taste in mildly symptomatic outpatients with SARS-CoV-2 infection. *JAMA*. 2020;323:6771. doi: 10.1001/jama.2020.6771.

6. Giacomelli A, Pezzati L, Conti F, Bernacchia D, Siano M, Oreni L, et al. Self-reported olfactory and taste disorders in SARS-CoV-2 patients: a cross-sectional study. *Clin Infect Dis*. 2020;26:330.

7. Yan CH, Faraji F, Prajapati DP, Boone CE, DeConde AS. Association of chemosensory dysfunction and COVID-19 in patients presenting with influenza-like symptoms. *Int Forum Allergy Rhinol*. 2020;10:1–8. doi: 10.1002/alr.22523.

8. Brann DH, Tsukahara T, Weinreb C, et al. Non-neuronal expression of SARS-CoV-2 entry genes in the olfactory system suggests mechanisms underlying COVID-19 associated anosmia. *Sci Adv*. 2020;6(31):5801. doi: 10.1126/sciadv.abc5801.